

The Role Of Social And Humanitarian Sciences In The Education Of The Future Generation

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Abstract: *This article discusses the relevance of teaching social sciences, achievements and shortcomings in the field, creative and critical views on it and the need to teach social sciences in higher education, the importance of educating the younger generation in the spirit of patriotism.*

Keywords — Creative, active, spiritual maturity, creative thinking, motivation, censorship, social, political, critical, managerial.

INTRODUCTION.

The 20th century was recorded in the history of the development of human society as a period of revolutions in the field of science and technology. This period brought many inventions and discoveries in the field of science and at the same time, it also initiated significant and significant changes in the world of politics. As much as this period was rich in historical events in the history of the world, it also left a deep mark in the history of Uzbekistan. The greatest and noblest gift of the 20th century to the people of our country was the achievement of the independence of the national state of Uzbekistan. Because freedom from the oppression and oppression of colonialism, achieving independence in the literal sense was the long-awaited dream of our people. Thousands of children of the nation sacrificed their lives for this goal.

The independence of the national state of Uzbekistan, the great happiness of our people living free, free, self-determining and deciding their own destiny has been given to the representatives of today's generation. Huge development works were carried out based on the requirements of independence. Democratic reforms are deepening.

Building a new society depends, first of all, on young people, their spiritual world, professional skills. Therefore, in the formation of the national idea, high spiritual qualities, awakening national consciousness and common sense in the young generation, educating them in the spirit of ideological struggle for the fate of the Motherland, people and independence, to become perfect human beings with high spirituality. The science of "Uzbekistan history" is of great importance in the formation of lib, as well as in the spiritual growth of our people. Teaching of this subject in all higher and secondary special educational institutions and schools is determined by this high importance.

But preserving the independence of the national state, strengthening it politically and economically, and building a great state in the future is an incomparably complex and honorable task. , is shared by becoming a life outlook. It is impossible to form feelings of national identity and patriotism in the minds of the young generation without informing them

of their mother's history, without analyzing historical events and phenomena, without providing historical knowledge and education.

In the past, great scholars who made great contributions to the development of Islamic sciences, such as Imam Bukhari, Imam Termizi, Imam Moturidi, Burhoniddin Marg'inani, the great mystics Abdukholiq G'ijduvani and Bahauddin Naqshband, who have contributed to the spiritual development of our nation, have contributed to the spiritual development of our nation, as well as mathematics and astronomy. sciences; natural sciences such as medicine, pharmacognosy, mineralogy; In the fields of logic, philology, and social science, the encyclopedic scholars, such as Muhammad ibn Musa Khorezmi, Ahmad Fargani, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Ibn Sina, Mahmud Zamakhshari, Mirza Ulugbek, have made a special mention of each of them, not only our national spirituality, but also It is important for the scientists of this field to record their effects on the spiritual development of mankind one by one.

"A nation that does not know its history and forgets its past has no future." "The international community recognizes and acknowledges that our ancient and beautiful land is one of the cradles of not only Eastern, but also world civilization. There are many great people, scientists, scholars and politicians from this blessed land and generals have matured, secular and religious sciences, which have become an integral part of universal culture, especially knowledge related to the religion of Islam, have risen to the highest level in history.

Therefore, teaching the history of the Motherland as a detailed, basic subject in the educational system of independent Uzbekistan remains one of the most urgent tasks of our life today - it is a requirement of the time. The necessity of teaching social humanities is that we cannot build the future without knowing our past history. Social humanitarian sciences such as History, Philosophy, and Spirituality play an important role in inculcating in the minds of today's young generation the struggle of our people for independence for centuries, the essence of independence, that it is a great blessing, and instilling in their hearts the feelings of humanity, patriotism, loyalty, love, duty and responsibility. These sciences should educate the young generation in the spirit of

national values and moral qualities of our great nation: honesty, purity, justice, humanity, truthfulness, hard work and humility, faith and belief, and instill in them a sense of loyalty to the Motherland and the people.

Social sciences are among the sciences that occupy an important place in the lives of young people. He encourages the future generation to think creatively and be active. It allows a broad perception of all the changes taking place in the society and encourages active participation in the life of the society. Raises spirituality, not to be influenced by foreign ideas, encourages to fight against them. Political maturity is achieved through the social sciences. The norms of critical thinking, correct creative approach to any issue are formed. It affects the development of speech, and through this, the spiritual and political maturity of young people increases and the ability to manage is formed. Social sciences teach to understand various processes taking place in life and play a strong motivational role in teaching ideas of creative thinking. Undoubtedly, social sciences are very necessary subjects in the education of the young generation. It would not be wrong to say that the teaching of social sciences is an issue at the level of state policy.

There are also some conflicting opinions and considerations regarding the teaching of social sciences in HEIs and the distribution of class hours. In this regard, President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev has emphasized many times in his speeches and has touched on the shortcomings in the field and the measures to eliminate them. The President's book "New Uzbekistan Strategy" published by "Uzbekistan" publishing house in 2021 mentions these and similar shortcomings in the field:

"Social and humanitarian sciences are of great importance in the development of our national spirituality, instilling it in the life of our people, especially our youth. Unfortunately, the development of these sciences lags behind the times. In particular, the science of history, which is extremely relevant for us, is no exception. Scientific research works on history are mainly conducted in narrative and journalistic methods. As a result, the essence of many events in our distant and recent past, the factors that caused them, and historical laws remain unexplained.

We must all deeply understand one truth: national history must be created with a national spirit. Otherwise, it will not have an educational effect. We need to teach our youth to learn from history, draw conclusions, arm them with the science of history and historical thinking. For this, first of all, I think it's time to develop the concept of development of the science of history in Uzbekistan until 2030. The Institute of History should be designated as a base scientific institution for the development of this science.

Also, stressing the need to financially encourage scientists and specialists in improving the quality and effectiveness of teaching social sciences, to further improve their working conditions, to make the monthly salary of the employees of the "Newest History" center under the Academy of Sciences equal

to the salary of the employees of the scientific research institute, and to strengthen its activities it is noted that

The place and role of the mass media in regularly covering the process of teaching social sciences in HEIs, showing the achievements and shortcomings in this regard and fully revealing the history of our country is incomparable. There is no such force as history, philosophy, and spiritual sciences that sow the seeds of goodness in the human mind and thinking, learn from mistakes, and become beacons for creating a bright future.

At the same time, under the influence of someone's subjective approach in this direction, there are frequent cases related to the introduction of a subject and the loss of another, the addition of departments and the excessive number of professors and teachers in them. "experiments", social science scientists and specialists, professors and professors have caused serious damage to the field. we don't need anything either. "It is enough to complete the tasks, teach our subjects and pass our classes on time." As long as we have these and similar problems, if we do not eliminate them, we will fail in educating the next generation," said the President of our country.

In the development of the field, attention is paid to the quality of educational literature. It is advisable to pay special attention to the theoretical and methodological aspects of creating textbooks on history. That is, based on the principle of objectivity, it is required to present historical events objectively, based on historical facts, and truthfully, without any fabrications or exaggerations. Events are presented in a scientifically based manner, relying on historical facts. Improving the quality of educational literature, simplifying the procedure for creating modern educational literature, accelerating the purchase and translation of the latest foreign literature, expanding the use of foreign literature as additional or alternative educational literature, and regularly updating library funds are important factors in teaching social and humanitarian subjects.

It is planned to develop a Concept for the Development of History in Uzbekistan until 2030. As a result of the adoption of the concept, the development of the field of history will be carried out on a completely new basis and systematically, and the process will be effectively managed. It will be possible to organize scientific activities in a purposeful manner and get a certain result from large financial expenditures.

Also, a series of works on the history of the Uzbek people and statehood will be prepared based on completely new scientific approaches that are in line with national interests. A generation of scientists with deep knowledge, creative and systematic thinking will be formed. A completely new system of training historians in higher education, inextricably linked with scientific institutions, will be created. The level of material and moral encouragement of scientists and professors in the field of history will increase. A new and effective system of promoting the ancient, rich and unique historical heritage at the national and foreign levels will be created.

In short, a state governed by people who are spiritual, rich in thought, and broad in outlook will never decline. Because the history of such a people is great, and its spirituality is high.

REFERENCES

- [1] Karimov I. There is no future without historical memory. Works. Volume 1, p. 81
- [2] Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Strategy of the New Uzbekistan. Tashkent: "Uzbekistan". 2021. 236-454 p.
- [3] Saifnazarov I. Why should we strengthen the social and humanitarian sciences?. Word of the people. 29.10.2021 No. 231
- [4] Mukhamedzhanova L.A. (2021). ROLE OF MORAL EDUCATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PERSONALITY. Bulletin of the Eurasian National University named after L. N. Gumilev. Series: Historical Sciences. Philosophy. Religious Studies, (2 (135)), 123-133.
- [5] Kadirova Dilbar Salikhovna, Inagamova Feruza Khurshidovna, Agzamova Nilyufar Shukhratovna, Mukhamedzhanova Lalikhon Ashuraliyevna. (2019). CATEGORIES OF HARMONY IN THE CONCEPTIONS OF CLASSICAL SCHOLARS. International Journal of Research in Humanities, Arts and Literature, (2), 293-300
- [6] Mukhamedjanova L.A. (2021). ROL NRAVSTVENNOGO VOSPITANIYA V RAZVITII LICHNOSTI. Vestnik Euraziyского natsionalnogo universiteta imeni L. N. Gumileva. Series: Istoricheskie nauki. Philosophy. Religiovedenie, (2 (135)), 123-133.